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A Place for Laughs in Hell. Martínez de León's Cartoons: Republican Humour in the Spanish Civil War

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In this article, we analyse the cartoons of Andrés Martínez de León, published in *El Sol* during the Spanish Civil War. Despite the war's brutality, humour emerged as a vital tool, serving both as propaganda and a connection to pre-war normalcy. Martínez de León's cartoons exhibit sharp satire, offering profound insights into the conflict. Our primary goal is to resurrect the work of this influential Andalusian graphic journalist and explore the narrative and visual techniques he employed. Through content analysis, we uncover how humour became a daily means of resistance, providing solace and commentary amidst the chaos and fear of war.

KEYWORDS cartoons, civil war, graphic humour, Martínez de León, Oselito

‘Humankind has created very few great symbols of itself. Don Quixote, Hamlet, Faust, Don Juan, me ... [...]. I like simplicity, humbleness.’¹

Martínez de León and Oselito, the Andalusí spirit

Andrés Martínez de León was among the most outstanding and renowned graphic journalists in Spain during his lifetime. The Spanish Civil War and the ensuing dictatorship, however, caused his name and his work to be forgotten. In recent years, although a recovery process has begun, it is still incomplete.² As a painter, cartoonist, writer, and journalist, he was a master of

¹ Andrés Martínez de León, *Oselito en Rusia* (Córdoba: Almuzara, 2012), 17, 24. Quotations in Spanish have been translated by the authors.

² Manuel Barrero, ‘Martínez de León y la promesa de la revolución comunista’, *Tebeosfera: Cultura Gráfica tercera EPOCA*, no. 5, 2017. <https://www.tebeosfera.com/documentos/martinez_de_leon_y_la_promesa_de_la_revolucion_comunista.html> [accessed 24 August 2023]; Rafael Alarcón Sierra, *Las crónicas de Joselito en Frente Sur, Frente Extremeño y Frente Rojo* (Madrid: Guillermo Escolar, 2018).

humorous cartoons. He contributed to many media, including writing and illustrating books, and his work stands out for its sarcasm and critical wit. For decades, Oselito, his best-known character, appeared on the pages of the Spanish press with his famous hat, a bow tie, and his hand in his pocket. During the Civil War, Martínez de León showed a clear commitment to the defence of the Republican side, and through his cartoons he emphasised his vision of the conflict as an avoidable savagery. All this makes his work interesting for the study of the relationship between war, humour, and propaganda.

Martínez de León was born on 5 April 1895 in the Sevillian town of Coria del Río but moved to the popular Triana neighbourhood in 1896. Living in this area influenced his training and style. His drawings feature bullfighting and traditional and local scenes inspired by his surroundings. In 1922, Martínez de León began his productive collaboration with the newspaper *El Sol*, published in Madrid. His comic strips were set in Seville, with typical scenes known to the audience in Madrid and, in general, to the Spanish public, for example characters from the worlds of flamenco and bullfighting, scenes of fairs and pilgrimages, or elements of Andalusian picaresque. During this time Martínez de León also published cartoons and drawings in newspapers and magazines such as *El Liberal* (1924–7 and 1933–6), *La Unión* (1924–9 and 1933–6), and the Catholic newspaper *El Correo de Andalucía* (1926–30 and 1933–35), among others.

In 1924 he introduced the satirical character that would bring him recognition as a cartoonist: Oselito, a popular character, graceful, with an elegant manner of dressing and living, in his gestures (his left hand was often in his trouser pocket) but also in his thoughts and feelings.³ The name – Joselito, with the ‘J’ aspirated as in Sevillian street slang – was suggested by the public due to his resemblance to the popular bullfighter Joselito ‘El Gallo’, who died in 1920:

My countrymen insisted that I look like the deceased José. The whole world insisted, and I, what can I say? I let them name me after him.⁴

Oselito was a hero who appealed to Martínez de León’s Sevillian roots in Triana and satirically criticised Spanish society. Martínez de León’s character became so popular that he was featured on a collection of wristwatches, a humorous publication was named after him, and, in March 1936, shooting of the Oselito film was announced.⁵ His reputation was such that the cartoons were exhibited in art galleries, including Madrid’s *Círculo de Bellas Artes*, to great public acclaim.⁶ He was compared, because of his significance to Spanish society, to Walt Disney’s Mickey Mouse.⁷

His appearance and, above all, his personality took shape over the years.⁸ From 1933, Oselito became a regular character in the newspaper *La Voz*. His creator endowed him with great social awareness and critical vision. In 1935, on the eighteenth anniversary of the 1917

³ Alarcón Sierra, 32.

⁴ Felipe Morales Rollán, ‘Mano a mano cinco chatos de manzanilla con el “Oselito” de Martínez de León’, *La Voz*, 16 January 1934, 4.

⁵ Francisco Canterla González, ‘Introducción’, in Andrés Martínez de León, *De Coria a Sevilla pasando por Moscú: escritos* (Seville: Diputación de Sevilla, 2012), xcix.

⁶ José María López Ruiz, *La vida alegre* (Madrid: Compañía literaria, 1995), 332; Canterla González, xcvi.

⁷ Morales Rollán, 4.

⁸ Canterla González, x.

Revolution, the newspaper sent Martínez de León to Russia as a special envoy. The author himself announced it in this way:

The only trip in the world that won't be boring: 'Oselito in Russia' against sorrows, against debts, against unhappy love, against rheumatism, against humidity!⁹

The outcome of the trip was the book *Oselito en Rusia (Oselito in Russia)*, published in 1936. Humorous and politically ambiguous, it presented a portrait of post-revolutionary Russia, alternating praise with criticism of famine and repression. The Stalinist regime though was not the main focus of his cartoons. In his funny style and in his characteristic language, Oselito linked the Soviet experience with the spirit of the Sevillian peasantry and the workers of the Sevillian neighbourhood of Triana.¹⁰

Oselito can be regarded as:

the caricatured, satirical and humorous alter ego of Martínez de León, [...] a fictional entity that, in a process of Pirandellian impersonation, ends up merging and confusing himself with his own creator.¹¹

The two 'formed a partnership that survived a monarchy, a republic and two military dictatorships'.¹² In 1935, the writer and art critic Sánchez de Palacios wrote:

It is often questioned whether Oselito is dominated by the artist, or the latter by Oselito. They are, I believe, so closely intertwined that they are slaves to their own preferences.¹³

Oselito reproduced the prototype – and the stereotype – of the Sevillian Andalusian from the Triana neighbourhood. He was ironic and critical, but also cheerful. He enjoyed himself in the pubs, with the Romani people, and at bullfights. He did not like to work and 'gracefully transmitted a whole world of popular wisdom through his speech and thoughts'.¹⁴ He was the 'representation of a certain Andalusianism that lies halfway between folklore and the suffering of the underdeveloped Andalusia'.¹⁵ Juan Ferragut described his representation of Andalusia as follows:

[Oselito] takes life as a joke, because, by dint of seeing pain at first hand, he has become accustomed to making fun of it, disguising his flaws with the blessed human balm of laughter. [...] He has always lived among the plebs who suffer, sing and moan [...] Oselito, the philosopher of the people, embodies the spontaneous and lively spirit of the

⁹ Martínez de León, 10.

¹⁰ Barrero.

¹¹ Alarcón Sierra, 31.

¹² Canterla González, x.

¹³ Mariano Sánchez de Palacios, *Los dibujantes de España* (Madrid: Nuestra Raza, 1935).

¹⁴ Alarcón Sierra, 33.

¹⁵ Antonio Martín Martínez, *Historia del cómic español: 1875–1939* (Barcelona: Gustavo Gili, 1978), 107.

people, is familiar with the dramatic side of Andalusia, the contrasting shadow behind the colourful and cheerful tambourine.¹⁶

In the words of his creator, the aim was ‘to reflect the psychology of the Andalusian popular genius, fleeing from the fake. [That is why] Oselito is a literary creation more than an artistic one. It is a way of being that many Andalusians bear within us’.¹⁷ Martínez de León himself recognised Oselito’s conception as his alter ego: ‘I already had him, without knowing it, inside me. I never thought of creating a certain “puppet” to symbolise this or that’.¹⁸ It was as if ‘Oselito was Andrés Martínez de León and Andrés Martínez de León was Oselito’.¹⁹

Martínez de León in the Spanish Civil War

The Spanish Civil War (17 July 1936–1 April 1939) was the central event in twentieth-century Spanish history,²⁰ but it also represented a turning point in the Western world’s awareness, as it foreshadowed the confrontation between progress and reaction, between democracy and totalitarianism.²¹ The war occurred because the military *coup d’état* did not achieve its fundamental goal, which was to seize power and overthrow the republican regime, and because, unlike what happened in other republics of the period, there was significant and widespread resistance, both military and civilian, against the attempt to impose an authoritarian system.²² The result was a three-year armed conflict that caused 500,000 fatalities and ended with the victory of the rebel side and the dictatorship of General Francisco Franco.

Propaganda, defined as the process of communicating ideas for the purpose of persuading and influencing people’s thinking and behaviour,²³ played a crucial role for both sides during the war. For the Republican side it worked as a tool to dominate the international projection of the conflict, as well as to maintain the morale of soldiers and the rearguard.²⁴ In this effort, Martínez de León was an active actor.

After the outbreak of the war in 1936, Martínez de León put his wit and pencil at the service of the Republic. He turned Oselito into a militiaman for several trench newspapers on the Republican side, where he continued to star in his adventures with his Sevillian dialect and his picaresque manner. As time went by and influenced by a visit to the trenches at the

¹⁶ Juan Ferragut, ‘Martínez de León, el humorista sin hiel, expone sus dibujos en el Círculo de Bellas Artes’, *Crónica*, 28 October 1934, 2.

¹⁷ ‘Entrevista de Manolo Lorente a Andrés Martínez de León’, *El Correo de Andalucía*, 8 April 1958.

¹⁸ José Blanco Díaz, ‘No todo lo que se denomina pintura taurina está hecho por pintores’, *Hoja del lunes*, 10 October 1955.

¹⁹ Virginia Mota San Máximo, ‘Oselito, de Triana al Kremlin’, *Ctxt*, 26 December 2018 <<https://ctxt.es/es/20181226/Culturas/23130/Virginia-Mota-San-Maximo-Oselito-Andres-Martinez-de-Leon-guerra-civil-franquismo.htm>> [accessed 18 July 2024].

²⁰ Julián Casanova Ruiz, *España partida en dos* (Barcelona: Crítica, 2013), 6.

²¹ Hugh Thomas, *La guerra civil española* (Madrid: Urbiión, 1979), 2.

²² Casanova Ruiz, 23.

²³ Philip M. Taylor, *Munitions of the Mind* (Manchester: Manchester University Press, 2003), 6.

²⁴ Armando Recio García, ‘Propaganda de la guerrilla antifranquista (1939–1952)’, (MA thesis, Complutense University of Madrid, 2015), 119–28.

end of 1936, Martínez de León became ideologically involved and denounced the brutality of the rebel army and the acquiescence of the Catholic Church.

From 1937 Martínez de León produced posters and drawings for the *Altavoz del Frente* – one of the newspapers of the Republican trenches – and provided engravings for Pedro Garfias’s book *Héroes del Sur (Heroes of the South)* (1938), an anti-fascist collection of poetry. His proximity to prominent left-wing intellectuals, such as Garfias, José Mas, Miguel Hernández, Luis Cernuda, and Rafael Alberti, influenced his work, increasing its dramatic and denunciatory nature. In this wartime context, Martínez de León illustrated the pages of Republican newspapers such as *Frente Sur*, *Frente Extremeño*, *Frente Rojo*, and *El Sol* with outstanding propagandistic and psychological work addressed mainly to the troops. As can be seen in the magnificent edition of *Las crónicas de Oselito en Frente Sur, Frente Extremeño y Frente Rojo (Oselito’s chronicles in Frente Sur, Frente Extremeño and Frente Rojo)* (2018), in the comic strips published in the Republican press distributed in the trenches Martínez de León attacked the insurgent side with determination and rage, resorting to a sharp sense of humour, a more aggressive tone, and provocative content. In his first contribution to *Frente Extremeño*, Oselito introduces himself as follows:

My status is more impressive than a fascist three-engine plane [...]. I am a man hardened by the war: the Madrid front, the Andalusian front, now the Extremadura front.²⁵

Oselito was ‘killed’ by his author in a cartoon in 1937,²⁶ when Martínez de León feared he would no longer be able to publish his comic strips. But he brought Oselito back to life to criticise important figures on the rebel side and to denounce their lack of humanity. For example, he grotesquely caricatured Franco’s appearance and scorned his military virtues. In *Héroes del Sur* he depicted the future dictator as a puppet in the hands of Mussolini and Hitler. In *Frente Rojo* the cartoonist laughed at Italians and Germans, referring to them in a derogatory way as ‘Macaroni’ and ‘Sausages’.²⁷

The cartoons analysed here were published as eight strips entitled ‘Oselito, in the fascist field’ in 1937 in the newspaper *El Sol*. The announcement of his contribution was met with high expectations.²⁸ The cartoons were later included in the book *Oselito. Extranjero en su tierra (Oselito. Stranger in his own land)* (1938). It consisted of the eight strips from *El Sol* and twenty-five more. The book included an introduction in which Oselito was credited as ‘a follower of Seneca’s thinking and thoughtful mind, the sharpness of popular irony and the clear and broad smile of Spanish humour’. Moreover, ‘he has been anti-fascist all his life’, ‘rebellious, popular, revolutionary’: ‘Oselito’s soul – people, people, people – is imprinted by the tragedy of the Andalusian land’.²⁹

Martínez de León returned to Madrid in 1939, where he was arrested and imprisoned on 8 November. His death sentence was modified in 1942 to a prison sentence of thirty years and one day. Though he was able to continue his work as a cartoonist – his works were smuggled out of prison – it was a particularly harsh period in his life. After being pardoned in

²⁵ ‘Oselito en el Frente Extremeño’, *Frente Extremeño*, I, 27 June 1937.

²⁶ ‘El humor en la guerra. Muerte temprana de “Oselito”’, *La Voz*, 14 February 1937.

²⁷ ‘Oselito en el Frente Rojo’, *Frente Rojo*, 23 September 1938.

²⁸ Canterla González, c.

²⁹ Martínez de León, 225.

January 1947, he returned to Seville and resumed his contributions to newspapers such as *Sábado Gráfico* and the weekly *Caireles*.

Oselito appeared again in 1956, stripped of the ideological baggage, in the satirical magazine *Don José*. Martínez de León continued to publish drawings and cartoons up to his death in 1978, although in the 1960s and 1970s his artwork focused on themes of minimal political significance.

Humour in armed conflict scenarios

Humour as therapy

The liberating effect of humour has been known since early times. References to it can be found in authors such as Aristotle, who granted it healing properties. Partly because humour is equated with the banal and insignificant, scholars are reluctant to tackle it as inherent to the human being and to be considered a valid tool to reach meaningful knowledge. As philosopher Simon Critchley argues, laughter allows a more pedagogical approach than, for example, the prevailing tragic–heroic paradigm. Critchley highlights humour’s ability to express even the most painful aspects of human existence.³⁰

Humour brings us closer to tragedy by allowing us to imagine the impossible, the unreal, not because it is unachievable, but because it does not exist at that moment. There is a rupture of learned logic, through theory or practice, when comparing a real situation and the imagined world, which gives rise to the laughable. This dialectic explains the frequent presence of the absurd in humour. According to this theory, humour occurs in incongruity,³¹ when a contrast is noted or some presupposed norm does not work. That is, the joke comes from ‘a subversion of expectation’.³² In fact, the inconsistency that characterises the joke led philosophers such as Kant, Schopenhauer, and Kierkegaard to take an interest in its study. Humour defies logic by distancing itself from the ordinary and from the codes that we assume to be stable, ‘but which in the hands of the humourist are dismantled and presented anew, showing hidden, deeper facets that confirm their mundane arbitrariness’.³³ Hence its subversive character.

This process of clashing realities, in which one is the universal and the other is the unusual or the denied, also implies an understanding of the miserable and a challenge to the normality that rejects the possibility of this exceptional situation.³⁴ Humour facilitates the expression of the forbidden, the hidden, and the humiliating, giving rise to pleasure, not only because of the joke, but also because of the liberation generated by the expression of a

³⁰ Simon Critchley, *On Humour* (London: Routledge, 2002).

³¹ Richard Godfrey, ‘Soldiering On: Exploring the Role of Humour as a Disciplinary Technology in the Military’, *Organization* 23, no. 2 (2016), 166.

³² Noël Carroll, *Humour: A Very Short Introduction* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2014), 23.

³³ Jorge Catalá Carrasco, ‘Vanguardia y humorismo gráfico en crisis: la Guerra Civil española (1936–1939) y la Revolución cubana (1959–1961)’, (MA thesis, University of Nottingham, 2011), 31.

³⁴ Laura Pérez Rastrilla, ‘El humor en la guerra: la desintegración de Yugoslavia a través de las viñetas de Franco Juri’, in *El humor en la historia de la comunicación en Europa y América*, edited by Antonio Laguna Platero and José Reig Cruaños (Cuenca: Ediciones de la Universidad de Castilla–La Mancha, 2015).

distressing situation that would otherwise have been impossible to express. In this sense, humour works as an instrument to achieve relief.³⁵

The type of humour known as black humour or gallows humour deals with subjects that in other discourses are met with rejection or embarrassment; these can be classified as inappropriate according to religious morality, such as sex; or they may be socially rejected as too painful, such as risk or death.³⁶ Tolerance of this type of humour is counterbalanced with discretion. Black humour jokes usually circulate underground or are restricted to a small community. This furtive character makes them difficult to study and to understand and even obscures knowledge and acceptance of them beyond the moment in which they serve their function.³⁷

Sigmund Freud was among the first authors to explain why we intuitively resort to humour as a response to stressful situations and the mechanism by which it can play a role in maintaining our mental balance. Freud reserved the term humour – differentiated from jokes and comedy – to describe the jokes shared between individuals experiencing negative emotions such as fear, pain, frustration, sadness, and so forth. This type of humour does not provoke laughter, but it has a strong appeal because of its impact on our spirits.³⁸

In addition to acting as an externalising instrument of the hidden or a tool for subversion, as mentioned earlier, a further function, in situations of stress, is to overcome negative feelings. The pleasure produced by gallows humour allows us to subdue – by substitution and suppression – feelings of compassion, anger, and even aggression.³⁹ In this way, humour works as a defence mechanism to assuage feelings of unease, distress, and grief.

In a context of war, humour allows the unmentionable to be spoken and operates as an escape route from extreme negative feelings. In a world where there is no fun, laughter itself constitutes a challenge to the conditions of life and offers an incentive to face a new, unknown, uncertain, and cruel order. Humour helps to shift the frame of reference of the situation being experienced and even one's own point of view but, unlike other defensive resources of the mind, without rejecting or concealing reality.⁴⁰ This distancing influences the mental health of individuals: it pushes away the negative feelings caused by the conditions of life,⁴¹ or by the memory of them,⁴² thus preventing one from being overcome by

³⁵ John Morreall, *Comic Relief: A Comprehensive Philosophy of Humour* (Oxford: Wiley-Blackwell, 2009).

³⁶ Norbert Elias, *The Civilizing Process* (Oxford: Blackwell, 1978); Karen Parkhill et al., 'Laughing It Off? Humour, Affect and Emotion Work in Communities Living with Nuclear Risk', *The British Journal of Sociology* 62 (2011), 324–46; Margot Coppin and Jean-Luc Gaspard, 'El humor negro frente a la muerte', *Desde el Jardín de Freud* 17 (2017), 149–60; Jana K. Rehak, 'Humour against Forgetting: Joking in the Space of Death', in *The Politics of Joking*, edited by Jana K. Rehak and Susanna Trnka (New York: Routledge, 2019), 70–85.

³⁷ Rudolph Herzog, *Heil Hitler, el cerdo está muerto* (Madrid: Capitán Swing, 2009); Viktor Frankl, *El hombre en busca de sentido* (Barcelona: Herder, 2016); Iva Jelušić, 'Joza Horvat's Tomcat under the Helmet (Part 1): On Soldier Humor', Christian Michelsen Institute (2023), <<https://www.cmi.no/resource/1642-joa-horvats-tomcat-under-the-helmet-part-1-on-soldier-humor>> [accessed 24 October 2023].

³⁸ Sigmund Freud, 'El chiste y su relación con lo inconsciente', in *Obras completas* (Buenos Aires: Amorrortu Editores, 1991), 216–17.

³⁹ *Ibid.*, 217, 219, and 97.

⁴⁰ Rod A. Martin, 'Approaches to the Sense of Humour', in *The Sense of Humour*, edited by Willibald Ruch (Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter, 1998), 15–60, at 44.

⁴¹ Martin, 42.

⁴² Liliana R. Feierstein, 'Graphic and Political Humour in Argentina: From Quino to *Página 12*', *European Journal of Humour Research* 2 (2015), 119–28.

circumstances while preserving a sense of self in the process of narrating it.⁴³ In this way, the use of humour during war could help those involved accept the reality of armed conflict, distract them from constant and extreme anxiety, and even improve their chances of survival.⁴⁴

In the context of the Spanish Civil War, Martínez de León addressed his humour to civilians, militiamen, and soldiers as a balm.⁴⁵ As poet Miguel Hernández, from the Extremadura war front in June 1937, said: ‘Oselito is here, and he is the one who makes me suddenly burst out laughing’.⁴⁶

Humour as propaganda

The study of cartoons is usually limited to their aesthetic and entertainment dimensions. There are very few studies of this format as a propaganda weapon despite its ubiquity in the historical milestones of the contemporary period and the mistrust, even censorship, directed at it. The causes of this underestimation have to do with a traditional disregard for visual products that are associated with leisure and popular culture. In the case of cartoons, their close link with satire and humour accentuates their perception as an inferior cultural artefact.

Humour is, however, a valuable genre for the distribution of propaganda, especially for messages aimed at a particular ideological community, given that humour is essentially social.⁴⁷ Laughter promotes the individual’s feeling of belonging to the group, creating and reinforcing collective bonds,⁴⁸ and therefore plays a relevant role in the configuration of identity.

The persuasive effect of humour lies in the fact that the scrutiny of the advocated position is less rigorous. This is in part because laughter brings us emotionally closer to the sender of the message and therefore, we tend to think that manipulation is less likely. It is also because humour is judged to be trivial, which makes us drop our guard in front of the laughable. The result is that both factors lead to an appearance of neutrality, indifference, and naivety, enhancing humour’s propagandistic effect compared with ‘more serious’ genres. Thus, humour is a frequent resource for the distribution of slogans and the reinforcement of messages. In polarised scenarios, this tendency is intensified, and it is common for humour to be aligned without hesitation with a specific political position.⁴⁹

Besides the psychological processes mentioned in its therapeutic component, humour ‘presents a simplified, highly memorable, newsworthy, and widely appealing narrative that

⁴³ Frankl.

⁴⁴ Marta Gorgula, “‘Oh, It’s a Lovely War’”: The Aims and Importance of Humour during World War I’, in *Histories of Laughter and Laughter in History*, edited by Rafał Borysławski et al. (Newcastle upon Tyne, UK: Cambridge Scholars Publishing, 2016), 33–6.

⁴⁵ Alarcón Sierra, 76.

⁴⁶ José María Rondón, ‘Oselito se marcha a la guerra civil’, *Diario de Sevilla*, 13 November 2018, <https://www.diariodesevilla.es/ocio/MartinezdeLeon-cronicas-Guerra-Civil_0_1297970644.html> [accessed 18 July 2024].

⁴⁷ Henri Bergson, *La risa: ensayo sobre el significado de la comicidad* (Barcelona: Marge Books, 2019), 20–1.

⁴⁸ Gregor Benton, ‘The Origins of the Political Joke’, in *Humour in Society: Resistance and Control*, edited by Chris Powell and George Paton (Basingstoke: Macmillan Press, 1988), 33–55.

⁴⁹ Catalá Carrasco, 85; Martín Martínez.

both entertains and informs'.⁵⁰ These characteristics facilitate an expansive outreach. In the case of comic strips, it should be added that cartoons or fictitious representations are more persuasive than real images.⁵¹ The portrayal of a non-existent or distorted being creates a distance, even a dehumanisation, so that the audience cannot consciously identify the real world in the drawings. The result is that the message is less challenged by the audience.

Because humour can conceal political messages, and due to its potential for subversion and defiance of hegemonic power,⁵² it is often perceived with suspicion in authoritarian environments or in times of crisis and even subjected to censorship.⁵³ For the same reasons, it is commonly used in scenarios of extreme and exceptional confrontation, such as in political campaigns,⁵⁴ as well as in armed conflicts.⁵⁵

In this way, comic strips can become artefacts of a propaganda war. This is the case of Martínez de León's cartoons. In them, in addition to the therapeutic facet aimed mainly at soldiers at the front, there is also a propagandistic one. In fact, the former can only be understood in relation to the latter. Martínez de León's work would not have been well received in all newspapers. Oselito's adventures, in the exceptional and brutal context of war, could only relieve and bring comfort to one of the sides. It would have been difficult for Oselito to provide the same liberating effect that he had for Miguel Hernández either on the opposite side or from a fascist newspaper.

El Sol, the newspaper where the cartoons analysed here were published, was founded in 1917 by Nicolás María de Urgoiti with the aim of promoting 'the political and social transformation of Spain' and as a supporter of liberal, progressive, and modern values.⁵⁶ On 31 May 1937, it was confiscated by the Communist Party of Spain,⁵⁷ renamed *El Sol. The Communist Party Morning Newspaper*, and was adorned with a hammer and sickle. It ceased in March 1939. *El Sol* had an unambiguous and explicit editorial policy and was an active

⁵⁰ Dmitry Chernobrov, 'Strategic Humour: Public Diplomacy and Comic Framing of Foreign Policy Issues', *The British Journal of Politics and International Relations* 24, no. 2 (2022), 277–96, at 278.

⁵¹ Christian Delporte, 'Humour as a Strategy in Propaganda Film: The Case of a French Cartoon from 1944', *Journal of European Studies* 31, no. 123 (2011), 375.

⁵² James Brassett, 'British Comedy, Global Resistance: Russell Brand, Charlie Brooker and Stewart Lee', *European Journal of International Relations* 22, no. 1 (2016), 168–91.

⁵³ Jennifer Musangi, 'A Zimbabwean Joke Is No Laughing Matter: E-humour and Versions of Subversion', in *Crisis! What Crisis?*, edited by Sarah Chiumbu and Muchaparara Musemwa (Cape Town: HSRC Press, 2012), 161–75; Stephen Gundle, 'Laughter under Fascism: Humour and Ridicule in Italy, 1922–43', *History Workshop Journal* 79, no. 1 (2015), 215–32; Cláudio Manoel, Alvaro Campos, and Alê Braga, dirs, *Tá rindo de quê? Humor e ditadura* (Brazil: Bretz Filmes, 2019) [Movie].

⁵⁴ María Jesús Pinar-Sanz, 'Humour and Intertextuality in Steve Bell's Political Cartoons', *European Journal of Humour Research* 8, no. 3 (2022), 16–39; Inari Sakki and Jari Martikainen, 'Mobilizing Collective Hatred through Humour: Affective-Discursive Production and Reception of Populist Rhetoric', *British Journal of Social Psychology* 60 (2021), 610–34.

⁵⁵ Delporte, 375; Lesley Milne, *Laughter and War* (Cambridge: Cambridge Scholars Publishing, 2016); Antonio Bentivegna, 'Humorismo gráfico y militancia durante la guerra civil española: La Ametralladora y L'Esquella de la Torratxa', (MA thesis, Ohio State University, 2017); Veronika Zangl, 'Politics of Humour in Extremis: Cabaret and Propaganda in the Netherlands during the Second World War', *European Journal of Cultural Studies* 25, no. 2 (2022), 389–405.

⁵⁶ María Dolores Sáiz and María Cruz Seoane, *Historia del periodismo en España*, vol. III (Madrid: Alianza, 1996), 26, 62.

⁵⁷ Juan Francisco Fuentes and Javier Fernández Sebastián, *Historia del periodismo español* (Madrid: Editorial Síntesis, 1998), 241.

defender of the Republic. Thus, with the publication of his cartoons, Martínez de León joined in the propaganda efforts of the newspaper's new management.

Methodology and research techniques

This research analyses eight comic strips published by Andrés Martínez de León in *El Sol* between 16 September and 13 October 1937, on pages three and four. (Only four of these strips are reproduced here.) In order to fulfil the objective of our research, we have analysed these cartoons using a mixed approach – graphic, linguistic, and semiotic. The linguistic–semiotic analysis and the graphic study of the cartoons verifies language features, graphic resources, and propagandistic elements.

Research into Martínez de León's work is an ongoing process. Neglect of prominent cultural figures in the pre-Civil War period is a common phenomenon. The subsequent fascist dictatorship tried to silence those who publicly defended the Republic. Manuel Chávez Nogales, Luisa Carnés, and José Luis Salado are examples of such figures who have been rediscovered in recent years or who still remain largely unknown.⁵⁸

The main reason for focusing on these eight strips is that they are part of Martínez de León's work yet to be recovered. They have not been analysed in any other work and can only be found in his original publications: *El Sol* and *Oselito. Extranjero en su tierra* – the latter with modifications. A second reason is that these strips demonstrate Martínez de León's previously mentioned commitment to the defence of the Republic, and therefore they illustrate how the author used humour as a relief and propaganda tool in the context of the war.

In the first part of the research, a descriptive methodology has been followed, which has allowed us to understand the historical context of the author and the nature and evolution of his character. For the study of the cartoons, a qualitative content analysis was conducted,⁵⁹ applied to the visual and verbal elements as a complete discourse.⁶⁰ The first step aimed at the selection of the body of the study, which involved searching the digital newspaper archive in the Biblioteca Nacional de España (Spanish National Library). Afterwards, the content of the cartoons was reviewed for a first filtering in order to identify coding categories.⁶¹ The coding categories were language, location of scenes, and characters.

In the second filtering, the connotations of the categories were analysed.⁶² The historical context and the author's biography were key to providing an interpretative

⁵⁸ Andrés Trapiello, *Las armas y las letras* (Barcelona: Ediciones Destino, 2019).

⁵⁹ Margrit Schreier, 'Qualitative Content Analysis', in *The SAGE Handbook of Qualitative Data Analysis*, edited by Uwe Flick (London: SAGE, 2014), 170–83.

⁶⁰ Philip Bell, 'Content Analysis of Visual Images', in *The Handbook of Visual Analysis*, edited by Theo Van Leeuwen and Carey Jewitt (London: SAGE, 2001), 10–34.

⁶¹ Darrin Hodgetts and Kerry Chamberlain, 'Analysing News Media', in *The SAGE Handbook of Qualitative Data Analysis*, edited by Uwe Flick (London: SAGE, 2014), 380–93.

⁶² Ayesha Ashfaq, Saba Ijaz, and Savera Sham, 'Drawing the Foreign Rivalry: Depiction of Indo–Pak Relations in Political Cartoons of Mainstream Pakistani and Indian English Newspapers (2014–2017)', *Global Regional Review* 4, no. 1 (2019), 8–20; Mutaz Mohammad Alkhresheh, 'Semiological Discourse Analysis of the Editorial Cartoons of International Newspapers on COVID–19', *Indian Journal of Forensic Medicine & Toxicology* 14, no. 4 (2020), 6169–79.

framework to place the cartoons in their own context and to identify the meaning of what was represented.⁶³

Finally, the decision to use the cartoons as the basis of our research is based on the conviction that they are a resource that allows us to apprehend the social and political reality of the time. As the results of the analysis show, the strips, through humour, provide information on the Spanish Civil War from a different perspective than the traditional historical approach as well as a new perspective on the use of propaganda through Oselito's light-hearted gaze.

Results: The remarkable adventure of Oselito

The eight strips are part of the series entitled 'Oselito, in the fascist field'. First strip, 'Oselito, in the fascist field', was published 16 September 1937. Second one, with the same title, on 20 September. Third strip, named 'Historical mistake', appeared in *El Sol* on 22 September 1937. Fourth was published on 23 September 1937 under the title 'Oselito, in the fascist field (III)'. Fifth strip, 'Oselito, in the fascist field (IV)', was released on 29 September 1937. 'Oselito, in the fascist field (V)', the sixth strip, was published on 2 October 1937. Seventh strip published on 5 October 1937 was titled 'Oselito, in the fascist field (VI)' and eight strip, 'Oselito, in the fascist field (VII)', was released on 13 October 1937. The series tells the story of Oselito, who is curious about life on the enemy side, and how he manages to cross the trenches and see it for himself. The title of the book in which the strips were later published – *Oselito. Extranjero en su tierra* – highlights Oselito's alienation and Martínez de León's discomfort with the war scenario. His priority, despite his commitment to the Republican side, was to achieve peace.

In the series, two dimensions of humour can be identified. On the one hand, the fear of death (strips 3 and 6) is made explicit in a humorous way, with laughter providing liberation by identifying a shared situation. On the other hand, the propagandistic dimension is displayed in the political nature of the cartoons – identification of the enemy, ridicule, and exploitation of differences between factions. By depicting the weakness of the enemy, the intention to raise the spirits of the Republican side and encourage them to continue fighting and resisting, in the hope of victory, can also be recognised.

⁶³ Giorgia Aiello, 'Theoretical Advances in Critical Visual Analysis: Perception, Ideology, Mythologies and Social Semiotics', *Journal of Visual Literacy* 26, no. 2 (2006), 89–102.

Figure 1. Caption: Oselito in the fascist field. First strip of the series. Published 16 September 1937.⁶⁴

The story begins when Oselito realises that, in order to find out what is happening on the other side, he needs to get closer. Despite the difficulty, he comes up with a simple solution that he refers to as ‘Columbus’ egg’ (strip 1; panel 4). The hero’s plan is not revealed until the next episode, leaving the reader in suspense. The reference to ‘Columbus’ egg’ (*El huevo de Colón*) is explicitly depicted in the third strip, which was published on the newspaper’s cover. In the second strip, Oselito’s plan is disclosed: he will take six bottles of manzanilla to Queipo de Llano, the rebel military leader who controls Seville.⁶⁵ His plan works: he penetrates the enemy’s camp. From this point on, the reader joins Oselito in his adventure. In the rebel camp he finds billboards cheering the supporters of the rebel side (strip 4) and soldiers from these states (strip 5). Finally, in the sixth strip, Oselito meets a Spaniard, whom he describes as a fascist. This makes him angry, as he is a member of another faction on the rebel side.⁶⁶ In the seventh strip, after drinking one of the bottles of wine to calm himself down, Oselito cautiously approaches another soldier. This time the soldier is a fascist. In the eighth and final strip, we witness the conclusion of the story, when Oselito manages to turn the warring factions on the rebel side against each other. Oselito celebrates his victory by drinking a second bottle of wine. Martínez de León concludes Oselito’s adventure with these lines: ‘in front of our southern lines and inside the enemy camp [...] The fascists were fighting each other ...’.

Figure 2. Caption: Oselito in the fascist field. Second strip of the series. Published 20 September 1937⁶⁷.

⁶⁴ Translations. Panel 1. Oselito was extremely curious to know how they lived in the enemy camp. - Will there be many priests? -he wondered intrigued- Would they have ordered more *sivilitos*? Panel 2. And so, he looked through the rangefinder, longing to peer into the tragic and grotesque world in front of him. Panel 3. But all the paths of his meditations answered the same: Switch to the enemy! Yes, yes! It's the only way,' thought our hero, 'but how do I make the move? Panel 4. But at last the solution emerged, clear, precise, marvellous in its simplicity. - The Columbus' egg! -Oselito exclaimed excited-. Except that my venture -he paused to to reflect- might cost me a little more than it did to Columbus!

⁶⁵ *Manzanilla* is a white wine produced exclusively in Andalusia. It is not mentioned in *El Sol*, but in the book.

⁶⁶ The rebel side comprised of different factions such as Carlists, monarchists, Falangists and part of the Spanish Army and foreign troops.

⁶⁷ Translations. Panel 1: Oselito, fully determined, went to put his wonderfully simple plan into action. Panel 2: And walked, on his way home, at a safe distance from the comrades who were digging trenches. Panel 3: The plan cannot fail,' -he said, walking towards the enemy-. Six bottles I had for the day we reached Seville. Courage! We must sacrifice ourselves! Panel 4: -Hail Purest Mary! Are you fascists? -he asked on the rebel

Distinctive features of the use of language

The language of the series is determined by Oselito's Andalusian origin. Martínez de León uses local expressions and popular Andalusian slang,⁶⁸ and he transcribes the dialogue phonetically. This is particularly manifested in the substitution of the /th/ sound by /s/, the loosening of consonants, and even the disappearance of syllables. In addition to the identification of the character with his geographical origin, using this variety of Spanish seeks to produce a comical effect, which is especially aimed at non-Andalusian readers.

The perception of the Andalusian as a funny, witty, and ironic figure has a long-standing origin. The literature and theatre of the Spanish Golden Age (1492–1659) propagated the amusing and histrionic image of 'a stereotypical Andalusian type, with little cultural background'.⁶⁹ Over time, the caricatured and *pícaro* image was consolidated and spread at a national level as a reference to amusement and entertainment. The accent and its wit are defining and easily identifiable traits. The cliché was so deeply rooted that in 1927, in an article published in *El Sol*, Martínez de León's own newspaper, the philosopher José Ortega y Gasset said that the Andalusian, 'instead of making an effort to live, lives in order not to make an effort, he makes the avoidance of effort the principle of his existence'.⁷⁰

The eight strips reveal three characteristics typical of the Andalusian language. The first is shortened words, for example *cura*, *pué*, *fallá*, and *desi*.⁷¹ The second is expressions typical of the Andalusian dialect, such as *olé* and *arma*.⁷² Thirdly, the author resorts to Spanish pronunciation variants, for instance *er*, *fasista*, and *sarto*.⁷³

Oselito speaks in a colloquial style that is easy to understand and that would have been familiar to the vast majority of the Spanish population at the time. The text is in the third person when describing Oselito's actions; elsewhere it is in the form of dialogue – between the main character and the other characters – or monologue. Informality is another feature of the language.

Location of scenes

Martínez de León places Oselito's adventures in the enemy trenches. 'The fascist field', as defined in the series' title, is portrayed as a 'tragic and grotesque world'. Architectural details

barricade. -At God's and yours's service -replied the *sivilito*- What do you bring? -This is for Queipo. -Come in, come in right away. And Oselito came in.

⁶⁸ Alarcón Sierra, 19.

⁶⁹ Leticia Ureña Rodríguez, 'España contra Andalucía, o la vigencia mediática de ciertos tópicos lingüísticos', in *La lengua en el candelero. Repercusión mediática de asuntos lingüísticos*, edited by Francisco Manuel Carriscondo Esquivel (Vigo: Academia del Hispanismo, 2014), 176.

⁷⁰ José Ortega y Gasset, *Obras Completas. Tomo VI (1941–1955)* (Madrid: Taurus-Fundación Ortega y Gasset, 2006), 180.

⁷¹ *Curas* [priests], *puede* [can], *fallar* [fail], *decir* [say].

⁷² *Alma* [soul].

⁷³ *El* [the], *fasista* [fascist], *salto* [leap].

are scarce. The artist pays more attention to the characters, describing the different factions and origins of the soldiers on the rebel side.

It should be noted that the Republican side is only depicted twice (in strips 1 and 2). In the first representation it can only be deduced that the character is in a trench. In panel 2 (strip 2), two characters appear in the background, digging in the trenches, dressed in militia clothing. Oselito describes them as ‘comrades’. Thus, the Republican side is only the background, about which he gives very little information.

The propagandistic intention is channelled by focusing on the enemy side. On the one hand, with the absence of the Republican side, the author avoids emphasising its internal disagreements. On the other hand, representing the weaknesses of the enemy serves to highlight the common ground among the Republican side itself, thus reinforcing unity.

Characters

Like other celebrated cartoonists, Martínez de León aims to condense a situation in a small space in a comprehensible way, using elements that are recognisable to the reader.⁷⁴ This is particularly evident in the depiction of the characters.

The main character is Oselito. In the series, Martínez de León preserves his distinctive traits: he is credulous, curious, and confident, even in the context of the war. He always dresses elegantly, in a suit, and walks with conviction with his hand in his pocket, denoting a certain cockiness. Oselito maintains his link with Andalusia through his language and through his appearance, especially with his characteristic Cordovan hat. By maintaining Oselito’s personality, the author perseveres, firstly, with the representation of the Andalusian peasantry and workers, but also with the reinforcement of stereotypes about Andalusians.

Oselito’s reactions – verbal and visual – convey some of the key humour of the series. For example, once he has the idea of bribing the enemy with bottles of wine, he always carries them with him (strips 2, 4, 5, 6, 7, and 8). The bottles, in the end, do not reach their intended target and it is Oselito himself who ends up drinking them to cope with the tensions within the enemy field (strip 7) and to celebrate his achievement (strip 8).

The fun emerges by making a potentially fatal situation, such as the chance that Oselito will be killed by the enemy, trivial and laughable.⁷⁵ It is a way to represent and talk about fear as well. We might laugh in war, but the enemy is real; war is a dangerous place to be, and we might die there. Therefore, even in fun, threat and risks are not hidden.

Oselito also plays a role in the destruction of soldier stereotypes through humour. The heroic and martyr-like image of soldiers is challenged by his own personality and, later, by his adventure. It is remarkable that Martínez de León does not portray the enemy in order to do so, but rather a Republican soldier. Oselito is curious and clumsy instead of brave and militarily trained, and this is what keeps him alive and leads him to victory. His achievements are the outcome of chance, even mistakes and blunders. The incongruity between what we

⁷⁴ Andrea Donofrio, ‘El Roto y el nacionalismo: las viñetas como instrumento de reflexión y crítica’, *IC-Revista Científica de Información y Comunicación* 18 (2021), 313.

⁷⁵ Alex Watson, ‘Self-Deception and Survival: Mental Coping Strategies on the Western Front, 1914–18’, *Journal of Contemporary History* 41 (2006), 254.

expect from a soldier and Oselito's behaviour and personality makes us laugh. There is an explosive joy in his survival. But in addition, the fact that survival occurs because of an absurd situation challenges the severity of military training while at the same time breaking down stereotypes. In a different context, such a critical questioning of one's own side might lead to a death sentence.

Christopher Columbus is also a character in the series (strip 3). He appears in a single panel, entitled 'Historical mistake', where Oselito asks Columbus: 'Why did you discover them?' The joke is that the simple plan he has come up with to satisfy his curiosity about how life is on the other side could prove catastrophic. There is no propagandistic intention; it merely fulfils a therapeutic function, using a metaphor easily recognisable for the readers. It is an expression used to describe something that seemed complex or difficult, but is easy or straightforward once understood. The core of the joke lies in Oselito's fear of being killed, and he blames Columbus for it by playing with the expression used in Spanish – 'Columbus' egg' – to describe clever and effective, but simple, ideas.

Figure 3. Caption: Historical mistake. Oselito blames Columbus for his fate. Third strip of the series. Published 22 September 1937.⁷⁶

The limited representation of Republican soldiers (strips 1 and 2) has already been mentioned, but it is worth considering also the humble appearance of their clothes, their hard work, and the respect shown to them by Oselito in the way he refers to them.

All the other characters belong to the rebel side. In their first appearance they are portrayed as people who can be easily bribed with alcoholic drinks (strip 2). This is a humorous aspect and also fulfils the propagandistic function of belittling the enemy. They are serious (strip 1), arrogant (strip 5), hot-headed, and violent (strips 6 and 8).

Many of the characters on the enemy side are foreigners. Support of states such as the Third Reich, Mussolini's fascist Italy, Salazar's Portugal, and the Moroccans who joined Franco's army are one of the main points of criticism in the series (strips 2, 4, and 5). In strip

⁷⁶ Translation: Oselito: 'My dear Colón? Why did you discover them?'

4, huge billboards praise Hitler, Mussolini, and Salazar. The latter is called ‘Portuguese little man’, mocking his physical size and Portugal’s less relevant geopolitical position. The last billboard reads ‘Long live Franco!’. The humorous touch is that, in contrast to the huge foreign posters, Franco’s is a small, barely visible sign on which is written: ‘let no one know’. At the time the series was published, the different factions on the rebel side were fighting each other for power, and Franco’s leadership was not yet clear.

Figure 4. Caption: Oselito in the fascist field (III). The presence of Foreign Forces is noted by Oselito. Fourth strip of the series. Published 23 September 1937.⁷⁷

The humorous nature of the foreign characters in strip 5 lies in their representation in accordance with the stereotypical national image or the image of the politician associated with their states. Thus, the German is an enraged soldier who, in the few words he utters, alludes twice to Hitler. In the Italian character, who is gentler, the stereotypes revolve around pronunciation. Oselito addresses him as ‘Signorini’ and the Italian talks about ‘Sevillilla’ [Seville] and ‘Malaca’ [Malaga]. The Moroccan, whom Oselito calls ‘Moor’ and ‘son of Mohammed’, is hunched over his loot. Oselito walks away quickly – denoting a certain fear – and does not engage in conversation with him. Finally, the Portuguese soldier stands under a sign indicating that he is a *consumer*.⁷⁸ He is, however, annoyed at being addressed as such and tries to magnify his work through language, pronounced in Portuguese, which also adds a touch of mockery: ‘*Yo soy o terror dos grandes contrabandistas*’.⁷⁹ In doing so, Martínez de León emphasises the Portuguese dictator’s arrogance, despite his physical – and geopolitical – size.

⁷⁷ Translations. Panel 1: Long live Hitler! The enemy camp was plastered with large billboards like at a trade fair. ‘Long live Hitler!’, said one. Panel 2: Long live Mussolini! ‘Long live Mussolini!’, declared another big billboard. Panel 3: Long live Salazar! ‘Long live Salazar!’, cried a billboard over there to honour the Portuguese little man. Panel 4: A tiny, humble poster, at ground level, forced Oselito to get down on the pavement to read it. ‘Long live Franco!’, it said. ‘But don’t let no one know about it.’

⁷⁸ Person who collects taxes in order to prevent fraudulent trade in goods.

⁷⁹ ‘I am not *consumero* but the terror of big smugglers.’

Figure 5. Caption: Oselito in the fascist field (IV). Fifth strip of the series. Published 29 September 1937⁸⁰.

The Spanish characters are a member of the Guardia Civil – Spanish military police – accompanied by a Moroccan (strip 2); a *requeté* (strips 6 and 8) – member of a paramilitary group guided by the defence of the Catholic religion, the Carlist monarchy, and the fight against Marxism; and a fascist (strips 7 and 8). The Guardia Civil character, who safeguards public order, is the one who authorises Oselito to enter the territory controlled by the rebels. The comical element lies in the deception of the only official authority shown in the series – something that is reinforced by the fact that the Guardia, even in the trench, is dressed in full uniform. The demeaning aim is reinforced by referring to him as ‘sivilito’ – a distortion of Civil – and in the first words that Oselito exchanges with him. To gain his confidence, he greets him with a ‘Hail purest Mary!’, a religious expression that evokes the clerical style of speech and sounds exaggerated coming from a layperson. Moreover, as will be further developed below, the allusion to religious elements fulfils a propagandistic function.

After coming across so many foreign references and characters (strips 4 and 5), Oselito finally meets a *requeté*, a ‘very Spanish guy’, that is, ‘half priest, half soldier’ (strip 6). This description is full of humour with a strong propagandistic intention. The depiction of the *requeté* ridicules the nationalism represented by the rebel side by emphasising the Spanish stereotype as a sum of religion, army, and monarchy – the *requeté* wears what looks like a monk’s tunic and a crown. Furthermore, mentioning priests is intended to point to the Church as an enemy since it stood as a major opponent against the Republic, not only during the war but also during the years in which the Republic existed (1931–9). Thus, the references to priests (strips 1 and 6) have the purpose of uniting the Republican side around familiar symbols on whose rejection there is general agreement. Humour is present from the very beginning of the meeting, when Oselito exaggerates his flattery: ‘*Olé los fasistas bueno! Lo mejor que hay en plan fasista!*’⁸¹ The *requeté*’s excessive and violent reaction when Oselito

⁸⁰ Translations. Panel 1:- Hey, you... German -asked Oselito- What’s the way to my beloved Seville? -You’re lying! Seville is Hitler’s -replied the German, enraged- Lying! Seville is Hitler’s! Hitler! Is it clear? Panel 2: - Signorini -Oselito asked again, with humility this time, to an Italian-. The road to Seville, which way is it?... - ¡Oh, mio carissimo! -Mussolini’s servant answered- Sevilllllla, I don’t know. You can ask me about Málaga, Baleares... Panel 3: -A Moor, a little further away, counted and recounted his loot. The son of Mohammed grunted, and Oselito hastened his pace without speaking. Panel 4: -Consumero, my friend -asked again- The way to Seville...? -¡Consumero! -he replied in a mean manner- I am, so you know, ‘O terror dos grandes contrabandistas’ Portuguese! For Salazar! About Seville, I know nothing about it.

⁸¹ *Olé*, the good fascists! The best you can find in a fascist style!

mistakes him for a fascist seeks to exploit the tensions between the different factions on the rebel side.

Figure VI. Caption: Oselito in the fascist field (V). Sixth strip of the series. Published 2 October 1937⁸².

In strip eight, the last character Oselito bumps into is in fact a fascist. He proudly claims his fascist identity. He is an unintelligent character. He unhesitatingly believes what Oselito tells him – that the *requeté* has called the fascists lousy – and Martínez de León assigns him the attributes of an animal: ‘he runs around bellowing’. The fascist starts a fight with the *requeté*. They are ‘joined by more priests and more fascists’, who come bearing firearms and bombs. The series concludes with the message that the divisions on the rebel side constitute a war within a war.

Figure 7. Caption: Oselito in the fascist field (VI). Seventh strip of the series. Published 5 October 1937⁸³.

⁸² Translations. Panel 1: Oselito was desperate to find someone to show him the way to Seville when, in the distance, he spotted a very Spanish guy. Half priest, half soldier... Panel 2: -Olé, the good fascists! -he shouted to please him- The best you can find in a fascist style! Olé these guys!... Panel 3: -You are lying, you bastard! Amend your words or I'll kill you in the Holy name of God! Fascist, me? -and saying so, he place on Oselito's chest the point of his bayonet. -Well, my friend -mumbled our perplexed hero- who are you, then? -I am a 'requeté'.

⁸³ Translations. Panel 1: Oselito, to calm himself, opened a bottle and drank... Panel 2: feeling strengthened on the inside and lightened on the outside. Panel 3: And, with extreme caution, he approached a new character. Panel 4. -God be praised! -Oselito greeted in a quiet voice- hey, my friend, if it is not an offense, can we say 'Long live fascism!'

In the end, the key to the fun is the enemy's stupidity, which also makes it look weak. The enemy is easily deceived and is so caught up in his domestic battles that he does not realise that Oselito is from the Republican side. Rebels are demystified: they are not smart; they cannot be taken seriously, and as a result they lose power. Thus, this psychological mechanism has a propagandistic effect. The aim of the cartoon is to reduce fear of the enemy by ridiculing him and therefore to encourage readers to continue resisting and fighting.

Figure 8. Caption: Oselito in the fascist field (VII). Oselito rejoices to see how the enemies fight among themselves. Published 13 October 1937.⁸⁴

Conclusion

This article analyses the function of humorous cartoons in dramatic situations such as war. It shows how they represent an instrument for keeping in touch with the reality before the war, but also how they constitute an important propaganda tool. Both dimensions coexist in Martínez de León's cartoons. It is not humour despite the circumstances, but humour as a result of those circumstances.

It is a distinctive humour because of its own process of producing laughter and because of its propagandistic function. Freud recognised that one of the effects of avoiding feelings of compassion through laughter makes us hard-hearted. But, in return, it prevents us from activating alternative defence mechanisms that would alienate us from reality. Gallows humour allows us to continue thinking about what no longer exists and to recreate everyday life, which has been interrupted by horror, without falling into despair or madness. It makes us aware of the insignificance of the human condition, through surprise in the face of the absurd, transforming painful energy into a liberating release.

Martínez de León's cartoons present an intelligent, humorous vision of the Spanish Civil War. The author's political commitment is evident in his fierce rejection of fascism and Franco, and his sense of humour heightened this combative character. As has been demonstrated throughout this article, his work shows that the use of humour in the midst of a

⁸⁴ Translations. Panel 1: Can we say long live fascism?', replied the fascist. 'Of course we can! Of course!' 'It's just that...', stammered Oselito, 'the priest with the rifle told me that all fascists are lousy'. Panel 2: The fascist left Osé hanging and he ran around bellowing towards the "requeté". Panel 3: A fight broke out. More priests joined in on one side and fascists on the other. Oselito drank a bottle to celebrate his success and official reports from the Republican zone informed the following day: 'In front of our Southern lines and inside the enemy camp, intense rifle, machine-gun and hand grenade fire took place yesterday. The fascists were fighting each other...'

tragic event such as the Spanish Civil War was not an insignificant decision. On both sides, the trench and rearguard press included humorous cartoons and even encouraged the publication of magazines specialising in graphic humour. In the case of the Republican side, cartoonists such as Aguirre, Bagaría, Ley, ‘Bluff’, and Kalders Guasp, among many others, stand out.

With this research we shed light on the importance of graphic humour in the trench press. It offered an alternative approach to the harshness of the conflict, generating bitter and sometimes desperate smiles among Republican soldiers. The popular tone of Martínez de León’s drawings, the puns and misunderstandings, his peculiar phonetic spelling, and his jokes led to the success of Oselito, a character who, with sarcasm and simplicity, denounced the world around him. In the war, Oselito was a militiaman dressed in a tight-fitting suit and hat who showed solidarity with those at the bottom and condemned the violence of the conflict. The artist’s political commitment to the Republic is evident in his extensive production during the war. In fact, the success of *Oselito. Extranjero en su tierra*, where the analysed strips were published, was one of the reasons for his arrest, accused of ‘a furious diatribe against the supposed invasion of the national [rebel] territory by Germans, Italians and Moors’, while ‘ridiculing the tough figure of the *Caudillo*, the *Generalísimo* Franco, and making the General Chief of the Southern Army, Gonzalo Queipo de Llano, the object of his irony’.⁸⁵

In conclusion, Oselito’s cartoons stand out for their simplicity and effectiveness: with his popular yet elegant attitude, he makes fun of himself, and the enemy. Through his adventures, Oselito offers a calm perspective on the conflict and a sarcastic outlook. In this selection of cartoons and in most of his publications during the war, ‘his humour is both verbal and situational; [...] This light-hearted, direct, colloquial style, full of vulgarisms, idioms, popular turns of phrase and a diction that tries to reproduce Sevillian speech, gives a pleasant impression of spontaneity and immediacy. In this way, Oselito manages to make himself an accomplice of the reader’.⁸⁶ Martínez de León introduces us to a naive and trusting character even in such a traumatic context as a war, which provokes, as Miguel Hernández used to say, bursts of laughter among the Republican militiamen⁸⁷. Oselito illustrates how humour in the most adverse situations, such as a civil war, can be used as a source of resistance and emotional coping. Fun in such circumstances is an outlet and a way to maintain the sense of humanity in the face of the war’s savagery. Though brief, humorous and fun moments allow individuals to connect with their identity and their deepest emotions, becoming essential tools for resilience and psychological recovery, during and after war.

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Notes on contributors

⁸⁵ Martínez de León, 13.

⁸⁶ Alarcón Sierra, 72–3.

⁸⁷ José María Rondón, ‘Oselito se marcha a la guerra civil’, *Diario de Sevilla*, 13 November 2018, <https://www.diariodesevilla.es/ocio/MartinezdeLeon-cronicas-Guerra-Civil_0_1297970644.html> [accessed 18 July 2024].

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